

Analysis of Debye Waller factor and molecular dynamics simulation of Seryl tRNA synthetase

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Abstract : Aminoacyl tRNA synthetases are enzymes responsible for first step of protein synthesis. We studied the Debye Waller factor (B-factor) of Seryl tRNA synthetase (SerRS) and carried out classical molecular dynamics simulation of SerRS in the present paper. The objective is to study the dynamics of SerRS through the course of conformational changes in its catalytic cycle. We observed from B-factor analysis and MD result that the N terminal domain is more ordered upon tRNA binding. Notably, the tRNA binding also impart influence on the catalytic domain as well. This conclusion is based on our simulated result on SerRS in *Methanopyrus kandleri*. Substrate binding organizes the catalytic domain as expected. The effect of substrate is noted in the serine ordering loop (SOL) region. An ordering of the closed state upon substrate binding is noted and is suggestive of an opening-closing motion. The connecting loop is most disordered in the closed state. The conformation of the loop changes relative to the initial structure upon substrate binding. This indicates a domain organization and is suggestive of a communication between domains upon substrate binding. This is concluded based on the fact that the tRNA is not directly linked with connecting loop or the catalytic domain throughout the course of simulation. The effect of tRNA on the catalytic core is most dramatic in the motif 2 region. The motif 2 exhibit least conformational fluctuation, even in the open state, when tRNA is absent. This indicates that tRNA has long ranged electrostatic interaction with the catalytic domain. A hinge movement around an axis nearly parallel to H4 is found in the present study. The tRNA is responsible for this hinge type movement. The domains move in a hinge motion in the absence of tRNA (both in open state with tRNA and open state without tRNA). It is most important to note that the hinge movements of domains occur in opposite ways in the absence of tRNA in open state and in the absence of tRNA in closed state. This is evident from the change of the sign of the dihedral angle in the two cases. Clearly, the hinge motion brings the CCA terminal tRNA closer to the catalytic core which is essential for the reaction. We studied the dynamics of various conserved active site residues in the open and closed states. The active site residues are more ordered in the closed state compared to the open state and this result corroborates the B-factor results described earlier. The MD simulation result indicate important catalytic role of residues in motif 2 loop. Interesting influence of Zn²⁺ ion is observed in the Ser binding site. The paper presents the first study of SerRS dynamics and reveals various conformational changes hitherto unobserved.

Keywords : Aminoacyl tRNA synthetase, SerRS, active site, B-factor, molecular dynamics.

Introduction

Aminoacyl-tRNA synthetases (aaRSs) carry out the first few steps of protein biosynthesis. The aaRSs are responsible for the transfer of an amino acid (aa) to its cognate tRNA (tRNA^{aa}). The formation of the charged tRNA is the prerequisite for the peptide bond formation in ribosome. The reaction carried out by aaRSs (aminoacylation) is a two-step reaction. First, the amino acid makes a nucleophilic attack at the α -phosphorous of

ATP and forms the aminoacyl-adenylate (aa-AMP) intermediate and releases inorganic pyrophosphate. In the second step, the 2'- or 3'-hydroxyl of the terminal adenosine of tRNA attacks the α -carbonyl of aminoacyl-adenylate leading to the formation of aminoacyl tRNA (tRNA^{aa})¹⁻⁴. The aaRSs are subject to intensive investigation due to their biological importance and many puzzling properties⁵⁻¹⁰. Despite these investigations, lacunae exist concerning the molecular understanding of the structure-

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function relationship concerning this important class of enzymes.

At present the perspective about the function of aaRSs is based majorly on the data from time averaged structures (X-ray and NMR), biochemical methods and limited molecular dynamic studies of various conformational states of enzyme. Many physicochemical questions at the molecular level remained elusive about the molecular details that how aaRSs function. Since aaRS structure and function are idiosyncratic, each of them demands individual attention and analysis. It is established that a dynamic conformational cycle accompanies enzyme catalysis which involves different states and aaRSs are no exception. Crystal structure analysis and molecular dynamics studies showed that aaRSs changes through different conformational states during its function¹¹⁻¹⁸. Many of the conformational states are inaccessible by crystallographic or NMR analysis but accessible by molecular dynamics simulation. Further, each aaRS have its own structural features which poses a challenge to the understanding of the reaction carried out by that aaRS. It is necessary to carry out detailed analysis of aaRSs and the present work is aimed at this direction.

The focus of the present study is the Seryl-tRNA synthetase (SerRS). SerRS is a member of the class II aaRSs, and is responsible for the aminoacylation of cognate tRNA^{Ser} with serine. SerRS is a homodimeric enzyme belonging to the class II aminoacyl tRNA synthetases (aaRSs) (Fig. 1). The structure, primary sequence and aminoacylation by SerRS are studied in *Escherichia coli*¹⁹⁻²¹, *Methanococcus jannaschii*^{22,23}, *Methanobacterium thermoautotrophicum*²⁴, yeast²⁵, *Bos taurus*²⁶, *Methanosarcina barkeri*^{27,28}, *Pyrococcus horikoshi*²⁹, *Thermus thermophilus*³⁰⁻³⁴, *Homo sapience*³⁵⁻³⁷ and various other organisms³⁸⁻⁴¹.

As a starting point to investigate the conformational states of SerRS through the course of the reaction, we analyzed the Debye Waller factor (B-factor) of residues of SerRS from various substrate bound and unbound crystal structures of the following species : *Thermus thermophilus*, *Pyrococcus horikoshi*, *Methanosarcina barkeri*, *Methanopyrus kandleri* and *Homo sapience*. The B-factor of crystal structure SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri* and those from classical MD simulation are compared. The dynamics of various conserved active site residues are investigated using molecular dynamics simulation.

Fig. 1. (a) The monomeric structure of SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri* bound with tRNA (3W3S.pdb) and (b) monomeric structure showing its domains, motifs in catalytic domain and loops.

To identify the conserved residues in the active site, we have performed multiple sequence alignment of primary sequences of SerRS of the following species : *Homo*

sapience, *Thermus thermophilus*, *Trypanosoma brucei*, *Pyrococcus horikoshi*, *Mus musculus*, *Aquifex aeolicus*, *Bos taurus*, *Candida albicans*, *Escherichia coli*, *Methanosarcina barkeri* and *Methanopyrus kandleri*. The objective was to identify the conserved residues in the active site region and other domains of SerRS. The multiple sequence alignment of *Homo sapience*, *Thermus thermophilus*, *Trypanosoma brucei*, *Pyrococcus horikoshi*, *Mus musculus*, *Aquifex aeolicus*, *Bos taurus*, *Candida albicans*, *Escherichia coli*, *Methanosarcina barkeri*, *Methanopyrus kandleri* are shown in Fig. S18 in the Supporting information. The result shows that only fourteen residues are conserved in SerRS in bacteria, archaea, eucaryotes including methanogenic archaea. Multiple sequence alignment results excluding the methanogenic archaea (MB and MK) are shown in Fig. S19 in the Supporting information. Results show significantly more conservation (total thirty eight conserved residues). The result indicates that the active site organization of methanogenic species is different compared to those in the other organisms considered and difference is pronounced in the serine binding site. A significant difference is noted in substrate (Ser) binding pocket that Thr271, Glu273, Glu325 and Ala428 (numbering scheme as per sequence of HS) are present in HS, TT, TB, PH, MM, AA, BT, CA and EC while Ala304, Cys306, Glu355 and Gly486 (numbering scheme as per sequence of MB). Additionally, Cys461 (numbering scheme as per sequence of MB) is present in methanogenic archaea and the corresponding conserved residue (including HS) with observed substitution is Thr429. Considering all, the number of conserved residues are only six. It is interesting that the same aminoacylation reaction proceeds in the SerRS from different organisms despite so much variation in structural organization of the active site. It is expected that the participation of active site residues must be different. However, little is known in this direction. In view of the several differences and similarities mentioned as above, there exist lacunae of knowledge exist about the structure and dynamics of SerRS that need to be addressed at molecular detail. Looking at the structural differences and residues present in the active site, it is apparent that the catalytic mechanism and dynamics of methanogenic species are not well understood. The details of the computation are presented in the Supporting information.

The results are discussed in the following section.

Results and discussion

In the following subsections, we describe the analysis of B-factors from crystal data and compared with MD simulation result. This is followed by results from MD simulation showing the dynamic features of SerRS.

Analysis of B-factors from crystallographic and simulation :

The B-factors of various residues computed only from C_{α}^N agree qualitatively very well with those obtained from complete amino acid residues (including the side chains) for all species considered (Figs. 2-6, S1-S6) as expected. The crystallographic B-factors of *Thermus thermophilus* are shown in Figs. 2-3 and S1 in the Supporting information, respectively. The comparison of the B-factors of residues of aaRS in the N-terminal domain (which is interacting with tRNA) is presented in Fig. 2. The tRNA is bound with the B chain in 1SER.pdb as shown in Fig. 2 and the lowering of B-factor is evident from the plot.

Fig. 2. Debye Waller factor (B-factor) of the N-terminal domain of SerRS from *Thermus thermophilus* (A chain and B chain of 1SER.pdb) : (a) based on the C_{α}^N and (b) averaged over all atoms of each residue (including side chains).

Fig. 3. The Debye Waller factor (B-factor) of the catalytic domain of SerRS from *Thermus thermophilus* (A chain of 1SER.pdb without tRNA and B chain bound with tRNA) : (a) B-factor based on C_α^N of each residue and (b) B-factor averaged over all atom of each residue (including side chains).

Fig. 4. The Debye Waller factor (B-factor) of the catalytic domain of SerRS from *Methanosarcina barkeri* (A chain of 2CIM.pdb, 2CJA.pdb and 2CJB.pdb) : (a) B-factor based on C_α^N of each residue and (b) B-factor averaged over all atom of each residue (including side chains).

Fig. 5. The Debye Waller factor (B-factor) of SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri* (3W3S.pdb) : (a) B-factor based on C_{α}^N of each residue and (b) B-factor are averaged over all atom of each residue (including side chains).

Fig. 6. Comparison of the Debye Waller factor (B-factor) of SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri* (3W3S.pdb) with the B-factors obtained from MD simulation in the following states : open state with tRNA, closed state with tRNA, open state without tRNA. B-factor are based on C_{α}^N of each residue : (a) N-terminal domain and (b) catalytic domain.

(a)

(b)

Fig. S1. The Debye Waller factor (B-factor) of the catalytic domain of SerRS from *Thermus thermophilus* (A chain of 1SER.pdb and 1SET.pdb) : (a) B-factor based on C_{α}^N of each residue and (b) B-factor averaged over all atom of each residue (including side chains).

(a)

(b)

Fig. S2. The Debye Waller factor (B-factor) of the catalytic domain of SerRS from *Methanosarcina barkeri* (A chain of 2CIM.pdb and 2CJB.pdb) : (a) B factor based on C_{α}^N of each residue and (b) B-factor averaged over all atom of each residue (including side chains).

(a)

(b)

Fig. S3. The Debye Waller factor (B-factor) of the catalytic domain of SerRS from *Pyrococcus horikoshii* (A chain of 2DQ0.pdb and 2ZR3.pdb) : (a) B-factor based on C_α^N of each residue and (b) B-factor averaged over all atom of each residue (including side chains).

(a)

(b)

Fig. S4. The Debye Waller factor (B-factor) of the catalytic domain of SerRS from *Pyrococcus horikoshii* (A chain of 2ZR2.pdb and 2ZR3.pdb) : (a) B-factor based on C_α^N of each residue and (b) B-factors are averaged over all atom of each residue (including side chains).

Fig. S5. Comparison of the Debye Waller factor (B-factor) of SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri* (3W3S.pdb) and those from MD simulation in the following states : open state with tRNA, closed state with tRNA, open state without tRNA. B-factor are averaged over all atom of each residue (including side chains).

(a)

(b)

Fig. S6. The Debye Waller factor (B-factor) of the SerRS from *Homo sapiens* (3VBB.pdb) : (a) B-factor based on C_{α}^N of each residue and (b) B-factor averaged over all atom of each residue (including side chains).

What is interesting is that tRNA binding brings order to the catalytic domain as well. This is shown in Fig. 3 and noted in the motif 2 region close to the interface of the two monomers. These regions are the regions where the tRNA can impart its influence to the monomer un-

bound with tRNA through interaction via bound monomer and the regions which take part in organizing the substrate for reaction. The result suggests domain-domain communication. The influence of substrate binding is observed in Fig. S1 in the Supporting information. The

adenylate bound state (1SET.pdb) shows lower B-factor compared to open state (A chain of 1SER.pdb) where the adenylate is interacting with the aaRS. These regions are starting from motif 2 loop (Phe255-Val272) which binds with ATP, motif 2 beta sheet (His273-Leu283) which interacts with both ATP and serine, beta sheet comprising Pro338-Ser348 which interacts ATP, Asp354 to tyr373 interacting with serine to motif 3 (Leu377 to Leu392) which interacts with both serine and ATP.

Similar influence of substrate is observed in the case of SerRS from *Methanosarcina barkeri* (Figs. 4 and S2). The comparison of B-factors of crystal in the open state (2CIM.pdb), closed state with ATP (2CJA.pdb) and closed state with adenylate (2CJ9.pdb) are compared in Fig. 4. The B-factor of open state is higher than both ATP bound and adenylate bound closed states for the residues in the loop region close to ATP (Val254 to Tyr259). Similar trend is noted in the helix close to serine binding region (Cys302 to Pro308). The influence of the presence of substrate is evident in Fig. S2. The smaller value of B-factor is noted in the closed state bound with serine (2CJB.pdb) compared to the open state (2CIM.pdb). This is noted in the loop region of catalytic domain (Val254-Tyr259), motif 2 (beta sheet 2) and motif 3 where the B-factor for closed state is lower compared to open state.

The B-factor values of *Pyrococcus horikoshi* show similar influence of substrates on catalytic region. This is shown in Fig. S3 and Fig. S4 respectively. The B-factors from the AMP bound (2ZR2.pdb) and adenylate bound (2DQ0.pdb) have lower B-factor values compared to the unbound state (2ZR3.pdb).

The available crystal structure of SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri* contains adenylate and no open state is available. The B-factors are shown in Fig. 5. The connecting loop, helix-loop-helix, serine ordering loop regions are significantly disordered as concluded from the higher peaks of B-factor. Although the tRNA is bound in the crystal structure, it is not in conformation suitable for charging (Fig. 1b). The comparison of crystallographic and simulated B-factors is shown in Figs. 6 and S5 and related discussions are presented in the following subsection. The crystal structure of *Homo sapience* does not contain any substrate and also several residues are missing as shown in Fig. S6, respectively. The N-terminal domain is composed of helices connected with loop and

is disordered. The structure contains a number of loops and these are the disordered regions. This is reflected in the high value of B-factor of *Homo sapience*.

Summarizing, the general conclusion about the ordering of residues in various domains of SerRS as observed from the different organisms considered are as follows. The N-terminal domain is more ordered upon tRNA binding. However it remains disordered until the binding of tRNA happens in the conformation which is not ready for charging step. The tRNA binding also impart influence on the catalytic domain as well (motif 2 is more ordered). Substrate binding orders the catalytic domain as expected.

Molecular dynamics result :

We further computed B-factors from simulated MD trajectory and compared with the crystal data to assess the quality of the simulation and to have basic understanding of the various dynamic states of SerRS. The comparison of the crystallographic B-factors and simulation result for MK are shown in Figs. 6 and S5, respectively. Due to the presence of the static disorder in the B-factor obtained from crystal, the baseline of crystallographic B-factor is in general higher than the simulated B-factor⁵⁴. This is shown in Fig. S5. When base lines are kept at similar level, the simulated B-factors have less disorder compared to the crystal structure indicating that the equilibration is achieved in the MD trajectory. The molecular dynamics results include three states (open state with and without tRNA and closed state with tRNA). Fig. S5 demonstrates that the pattern of crystallographic B-factor and the simulated B-factor are similar. Exception is the Helix-Loop-Helix (HLH) region of catalytic domain where the simulated B-factor is higher than the crystallographic B-factor. This discrepancy is for the following reason. HLH region is protruded out from the catalytic core and is a flexible unit between motif 1 connected via large loop with motif 2 in the simulated monomer state (Fig. 1b) where the crystallographic packing is absent (Fig. 1a) and motions are unrestricted. This is also noted from the RMSD of HLH region (Fig. S7). The B-factor of N-terminal domain is lowest for most residues in the closed state with tRNA and is consistent with the fact that the state is expected to be more ordered than the open state due to substrate binding. The B-factor of N-terminal domain increases upon removal of tRNA and indicates that the N-terminal domain is ordered in tRNA

bound state. This is shown in Fig. 6. The tRNA unbound crystal is unavailable for *Methanopyrus kandleri*. However, such effect is observed in the case of *Thermus thermophilus*. The N-terminal domain is most disordered (higher RMSD) for *Methanopyrus kandleri* when tRNA is removed and is expected. This is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. S7. The root mean square deviation (RMSD) with respect to the initial structure (in Å) of the backbone of the Helix-Loop-Helix (HLH) region of monomer of SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri* for open state with tRNA, closed state with tRNA and open state without tRNA from MD simulation data.

Fig. 7. The root mean square deviation (RMSD) of backbone with respect to the initial structure (in Å) of the N-terminal domain region of monomer of SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri* for open state with tRNA, closed state with tRNA and open state without tRNA from MD simulation data.

The influence of tRNA is not pronounced in C terminal domain as the domain is not directly in contact with tRNA and experience only indirect influence. The effect of substrate is noted in the serine ordering loop (SOL) region as shown in Fig. S8 in the Supporting informa-

Fig. S8. The B-factor of serine ordering loop of monomer of SerRS with respect to the initial structure (in Å) from *Methanopyrus kandleri* for open state with tRNA, closed state with tRNA and open state without tRNA with respect to C_{α}^N of each residue from MD simulation data.

tion. The B-factor of the closed state is reduced compared to the open state in the SOL region. This suggests an ordering of the closed state upon substrate binding and an opening-closing motion. Our molecular dynamics result shows that the connecting loop is more disordered (Fig. S9 in the Supporting information). However, another interesting feature is that the loop is most disordered in the closed state. Since the RMSD is computed with respect to the initial structure (which was started from an adenylate bound 3W3S.pdb), the conformation of the loop changes upon substrate binding. This also indicates a communication between domains upon sub-

Fig. S9. The root mean square deviation (RMSD) of the backbone with respect to the initial structure in Å of the connecting loop of monomer of SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri* for open state with tRNA, closed state with tRNA and open state without tRNA with respect to C_{α}^N of each residue from MD simulation data.

strate binding. The effect of tRNA on the catalytic core is most dramatic in the motif 2 region which is more ordered upon removal of tRNA (Figs. S10 and S11 in the Supporting information). It is known that the motif 2 interacts with stem base (near CCA terminal) of tRNA. This indicates that tRNA has long distance interaction on the catalytic domain.

Fig. S10. The root mean square deviation (RMSD) of the backbone with respect to initial structure (in Å) of motif 2 of monomer of SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri* for open state with tRNA, closed state with tRNA and open state without tRNA with respect to C_{α}^N of each residue from MD simulation data.

Fig. S11. Root mean square deviation (RMSD) of the backbone with respect to initial structure (in Å) of motif 2 loop of monomer of SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri* for open state with tRNA, closed state with tRNA and open state without tRNA with respect to C_{α}^N of each residue from MD simulation data.

We observed an interesting hinge type of motion in the trajectory. Crystallographic study in SerRS from *Methanosarcina barkeri* shows a hinge type movement of

N-terminal domain around an axis nearly parallel to H4²⁸. Superimposition of the catalytic cores of each monomer of dimeric SerRS from *Methanosarcina barkeri* shows that a hinge type of motion (about 20°) is required to superimpose the tRNA binding domain. Same hinge movement around an axis nearly parallel to H4 is found in our simulated result based on SerRS in *Methanopyrus kandleri*. The tRNA is responsible for this hinge type movement which is shown in the Fig. 8. The dihedral angle ξ spanning two domains (on an average) retain a constant value through the course of the simulation in the closed state with tRNA. However, the domains move in a hinge move-

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8. Hinge rotation between N-terminal domain and catalytic domain of SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri* : (a) The definition of the dihedral angle (ξ in degrees) used to measure the hinge rotation between N-terminal and C-terminal and (b) ξ values from 500 ps trajectory open state with tRNA, closed state with tRNA and open state without tRNA from MD simulation data.

ment in the absence of tRNA (both in open state with tRNA and open state without tRNA) and a change in the ξ value is noted in the presence (open state) and absence of tRNA (open state). It is most important to note that the hinge movements of the domains are in opposite ways in the absence of tRNA in open state and in the absence of tRNA in closed state. This is evident from the change of sign of the dihedral angle in the two cases. Clearly, the hinge motion brings the CCA terminal tRNA closer to the catalytic core which is essential for the reaction. This is the direct evidence of influence of tRNA on the catalytic cycle.

Finally, we analyze the role of various conserved active site residues (we refer to Fig. S12 in the Supporting information) from the results of MD trajectory. The results are shown in Fig. S13 to Fig. S17, respectively. The Glu351 (motif 2 loop) interacts with the NH_2 group of Ade of ATP and exhibits interesting conformational fluctuation which is more in open compared to closed state. Similar trend is noted for Arg349 present in the motif 2 loop interacting with αP oxygen of ATP. The results are shown in Fig. S13 in the Supporting informa-

tion and Fig. 9, respectively. These two residues changes conformation in a more flexible manner, particularly in the open state, as their interaction is lost in the open state compared to the adenylate geometry. These residues change their conformation upon substrate binding and are more ordered in the closed state. The residues interacting directly or indirectly with Ser have shown rather lesser conformational fluctuation. This is shown for Ala317, Cys319, Glu368 and Cys478 in Figs. S14 to S17 in the Supporting information respectively. The trend of RMSD are comparable as these residues interact with Ser via Zn^{2+} which impart strong electrostatic interaction on the side chains and stabilize them as the ionic influence is spherically symmetric. When the Ser is absent, the side chains of the residues maintain their interaction with the Zn^{2+} and show no deviation from the closed state. Since the side chain of Ala interacts via weaker nonbonded interaction, it is more disordered with higher fluctuation as noted from the RMSD values. In summary, the active site residues are more ordered in the closed state compared to the open state and this result corroborates the B-factor results described earlier.

Fig. S12. Schematic diagram of the active site region of SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri*.

Fig. S13. Root mean square deviation (RMSD) of Glu351 residue including the side chain of SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri* with respect to initial structure (in Å), for open state with tRNA, closed state with tRNA and open state without tRNA.

Fig. S16. Root mean square deviation (RMSD) of Glu368 residue including the side chain of SerRS of the species *Methanopyrus kandleri* with respect to initial structure (in Å), for open state with tRNA, closed state with tRNA and open state without tRNA.

Fig. S14. Root mean square deviation (RMSD) of Ala317 residue including the side chain of SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri* with respect to initial structure (in Å), for open state with tRNA, closed state with tRNA and open state without tRNA.

Fig. S17. Root mean square deviation (RMSD) of Cys478 residue including the side chain of SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri* with respect to initial structure (in Å), for open state with tRNA, closed state with tRNA and open state without tRNA.

Fig. S15. Root mean square deviation (RMSD) of Cys319 residue including the side chain of SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri* with respect to initial structure (in Å), for open state with tRNA, closed state with tRNA and open state without tRNA.

Concluding remarks

The present work, for the first time, gives a view of the dynamics of SerRS via analysis of B-factor and MD simulation. The major conclusions of the paper are as follows. (1) B-factor analysis and MD result show that the N-terminal domain is more ordered upon tRNA binding. (2) The tRNA binding also impart influence on the catalytic domain as well as observed in the simulated result on SerRS in *Methanopyrus kandleri*. The effect of tRNA on the catalytic core is most dramatic in the motif 2 region. The motif 2 exhibit least conformational fluctuation, even in the open state, when tRNA is absent.

3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----MVLDDLFRVVDKGGDPALIR	20
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	--MGHHHHHSSGLVPRGSATERQDRNLLYEHAREGYSALPLLDMEISLCAYPE----	DAA
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----MLDINAFVLVEKGGDPEI IK	
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----GPGSMVLDIQLFRDETGA--NIIR	
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----MVDLKRRLRQEP----	EVFH
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----MVDLKRRLRQEP----	EVFH
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----MLDIKLIRENP----	ELVK
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----MIDINLIREKP----	DYVK
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----MLDPNLLRNEP----	DAVA
2CIM:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	MGSSHHHHHSSGLVPRGSHMKLQPNLK-----	AYFKTSADPTPAK
3W3S:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----MELKFSAEVE-----	LTLGREVDPAEIE
3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	ETQE-KR--FKDPGLVDQLVKADSEWRRRCFRADNLNKLKLN-----	59
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	RALDLRKGELR-SKDLPGIISTWQELRQLREQIRSLLEEKEA-----	
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	ASQK-KR--GDSVELVDEIIAEYKWEVVKLRFDLDEHNKLNLS-----	
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	ESQR-RR--FADPDIVDAIIEADKKWRRTOFLTEASKKLINI-----	
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	RAIR-EKGV--ALDLEALLAVDEQLHKQEV IADKQMSVKEDLDKVEPAVIEAQNAVKS	
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	RAIR-EKGV--ALDLEALLALDRVQELKRLQEVQTERNQ-----	
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	NDLI-KRGELEKVKWVDEILKLDTEWRTKLKEINRLRHERNK-----	
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	ERLA-TRD-KELVSLVDKVLLELDKRRREI IKRLEALRSERNK-----	
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	EKLA-RRG-FKL--DVKLGALEERRKVLQVKTENLQAERNS-----	
2CIM:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	DATA-----ALFEEANSTLLTRG--APEGQ----	
3W3S:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	PTVE-----EFVKEANEDLLQRG--VPTGK----	
:					
3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----	
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----	
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----	
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----	
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	IKKQHLVEVRSMANPPAAVKLALESIALLLGESTTDWKQIRSIIMR----	EN-----FI
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----VAKRVPKAPPEE-----	
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----	
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----	
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----	
2CIM:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----GAKVTEWKLGEDRIELTLQSGRYVRVHDAI	
3W3S:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----EGAKIESYVLYDITYMEITGTRYLRPHEAA	
3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----CSKTIGEKMKKKEPVGDDESVPEN-----	VLSFD---DLTAD
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----VTEAVRALVVDN-----	N-----
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----VQKEIGKRFKAKEDAKDLIAEKEK-----	LS-----
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----CSKAVGAKKAKEADGDTSEIPPO-----	VKEAYENGTLKGE
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	PTIVNFSAEIISDAIREKMKKNYM-SNPSY-----	NYEIVNRSALAG
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----	
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----IAVEIGK-----	
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----LSKEIGK-----	
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----RSKSIQ-----	
2CIM:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	FRLRQLAEALGKYYIGIRG--IEVESFIIKVPADHELRLKVPYIKSMEN--	IEGG
3W3S:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	MRVRKRLAERLGRKRVGVRD--LKI PRYEVVLRFDREVITYDYGVPVADDVVVEDGT	
3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	ALANLKVSQIKKVRLLIDEAIIKCAERIKLEAER-----	FENLREIGNLLHSPVIS
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	---SQ-VQDDPQYQSLRARGREIRKQLTLLYPKEAQLEEQFYLRALRPNQTHPDVVPV	147
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----NEKKEIIEKEAEA--DKNLRSKINQVGNIVHESVVD	
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	QVEQLCVLQKLSKDLSDQVAGLAKEAQLEEEER-----	DKLMLNVGNILHESVPIA
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	PMVKWAIACLNY--ADMLKRVEPLRNLQKLEDDAKDNQKLEALLQVPLPPWGPAPVG	
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----K--EALIARGKALGEEAKRLEALREKEARLEALLQVPLPPWGPAPVG	
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	---RRKKGEPV--DELLAKSREIVKRIGELENEVEELKKKIDYYLWRLPNI THPSVPV	
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	---LKREKQDT--TEIQNRVKELKEEIDRLEELRVEEELKNTLLWIPNLPHPSVPV	
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	---AKARGEDI--EPLRLEVNLGEEELDAKAEALDALQAEIRDIALTI PNLPADVVPV	
2CIM:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	IQLELEV-GEAEMKNRVPDRILTLLEEK----IEAAQ-----	YGAKAEHWNLWQREP--
3W3S:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	VRLTFQDVDEMLRRHVIDRIVIRLVAVAVEERSELVE----	RVTKVEPGTVVDES GP--
3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	NDEDVNDKVERIWGD-----	CTVRKKYSHVDLVMVDFGEFEGEK
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	DESQ--ARLVHVVDGKPAF-----	SFQPRGHLEIAEKLDIIRQKR
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	QDEEN-NELVRTWTPPE-NYKKPE-----	QIAAATGAPAKLSHHEVLLRLDGYDPER
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	QDEETGNTVVRTPGN-----	TTKRAKLNHVSIMERLGMMDTSK
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	GEE-A-NREIKRVGGPPEF-----	SFPPLDHALMEKNGWWE-PR
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	GEE-A-NREIKRVGGPPEF-----	SFPPLDHALMEKNGWWE-PR
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	KDEND-NVPIRFWVKARVWKGHLERPLEQSQGKMEYEILEWKPKLHVLDLLEILGGADPAR	
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	EDEKD-NVEVRRWGEPKRF-----	DFEPKPHWIEIGERLGLDFPKR
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	KDEND-NVEVSRWGTTPREF-----	DFEVRDHVTLGEMHSLDFAA
2CIM:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----MEHPFKED-----	PTQAMMKEGWLK----
3W3S:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----RRIRFRGD-----	VTBEARRRGVVK----

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3VBB : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-GAVVAGSRGYFLKGVLVFLEQALIQYALRTLGS-RGYIPIYTPPFMRKEVMQEVAQLSQ 242
1WLE : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-I.SHVSGHRSSYFI.RGAGATI.QHGI.VNFTI.NKTI.TH-RGFT.PMTV.PDI.I.RGVV.FRGCGM.TPN
3QNE : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-GVR.TV.GHR.GYFI.RNYGV.FI.NQAT.TNYGI.SPT.SS-KGVVPTI.QAPVMMNK.FVMAKTAQI.SQ
3LSQ : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	AVTSMAGGRSYVLKGLVQLQVALVSYSLDPLVK-RGYTPFYPPFFLNLRDVMGEVAQLSQ
3ERR : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-TSQVSGSRSYAI.KGDI.AI.YRI.AI.I.RFAMD.PMAR-RGPT.PMTI.PSYARE.KAP.I.GTGHP.PA
1SER : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-TSQVSGSRSYAI.KGDI.AI.YRI.AI.I.RFAMD.PMAR-RGPT.PMTI.PSYARE.KAP.I.GTGHP.PA
2DQ0 : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-AAKVS.GSR.FYFI.I.NE.VTI.I.DI.AI.TRF.AI.DRI.TE-KGPT.PVTI.PPYM.VRR.FV.RG.ST.SF.FD
2DQ3 : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-GAKI.SGSR.FVTI.A.GWGARI.FRAI.TNFM.I.DI.HTK-KGYKFT.CPPH.I.VK.PRTI.TGTGQI.PK
ESC : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-AVKI.TGSR.FVVM.KGQT.ARM.HRAI.SQ.FMI.DI.HTR.QHGVS.FENV.VPVI.VNQDTI.VGTGQI.PK
2CIM : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	---R.GSSR.GQW.T.HGP.QSAR.I.PRT.FFK.TVI.FEI.I.I.EPI.GYRE.MT.FPKI.VTW.FV.MK.SGHAKG
3W3S : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	---R.FPGR.GQW.T.VT.PP.MAAI.FEVI.RDFI.I.ERVTR.KI.GF.FPAI.FPKI.T.PI.E.TM.FR.MRYI.HG
:	:	:	:	* : *
3VBB : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	FD-EELYKVIKKGSEKSDDNS-YDEKY-----LIATSEQPIA 277
1WLE : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	AKPSQIYNIIDPS-----R-FEDLN-----LAGTAEVGLA
3QNE : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	FD-FE.I.YKV.TDGE-----DFKY-----I.TATSEQPT.S
3LSQ : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	FD-EELYQVSGDG-----DKY-----LIATSEMPIA
3ERR : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	YR-DQVWAT-----A-----E.TDI.Y-----I.TGTAR.VVTI.N
1SER : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	YR-DQVWAT-----A-----E.TDI.Y-----I.TGTAR.VVTI.N
2DQ0 : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	FE-DVTYKV-----E-----E.DNI.Y-----I.TPTAR.HPI.A
2DQ3 : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	FE-EDLYKC-----E-----E.DNLY-----LIPTAEVPLT
ESC : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	FA-GDLPHTR.PLEE.EAD-----T.SNYA-----LIPTAEVPLT
2CIM : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	VYPEI.YV.CPPQ.TR.DP.VY.WEE.VAD.YYK.V---THEVPT.KLI.EK.IA.EP.I.GC.MY.AQ.CP.PFW
3W3S : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	L.PDGM.YV.V.CP.PKR-DPEL.FDD.FKRELY.VW.GEL.NERT.LG.SLKE.KLR.DP.GY.VLA.PAQ.CE.PFY
:	:	:	:	* : *
3VBB : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	ALHRDEWLRP--EDLPIKY-AGLSTCFRQEVGSHGRDTRGIFRVHQFEKIEQFVYSSPHD 334
1WLE : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	GYPMDHSVAF--RDLPIRM-VCSSTCYRAETD-TGKEPWGLYRVVHHTKVMFPGVTGPGGL
3QNE : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	AYHAGWEWFESPAEQLPVRY-AGYSSCFRREAGSHGKDAWGI.FRVHAFKIEIQVLTPEP--
3LSQ : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	AYHRGRWFTE--LKEPLKY-AGMSTCFRKEAGAHGRDTLGI.FRVHQFDKIEQFVVCSPRQ
3ERR : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	ALHSGETLPY--EALPLRY-AGYAPAFRSEAGSFGKDV.RGLMRVHQFHKVEQVVLTEASL
1SER : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	ALHSGETLPY--EALPLRY-AGYAPAFRSEAGSFGKDV.RGLMRVHQFHKVEQVVLTEASL
2DQ0 : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	GMHANEILDG--KDLPLLY-VGVSPCFRKEACTAGKDTKGI.FRVHQFHKVEQFVYSRP--
2DQ3 : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	NLYREEILKE--ENLPIYL-TAYTPCYRREAGAYGKDIRGIRI.RHQFDKVELVKIVHP--
ESC : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	NLVRGEIIDE--DDLPIKM-TAHTPCFRSEAGSYGRDTRGLIRMHQFDKVEVQIVRPP--
2CIM : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	MYVAGETLPN--EETPVKVFDRSGTSHRYESG---GIHGIERVDEFHRIEIVWIGTK--
3W3S : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	ELLRDEVVDP--ERLPIKLYDCSGWTYRWEGG---AAKGLERVNEFQRIEHWVIAEP--
:	:	:	:	* : * : * : *
3VBB : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	NKSWEMFEEMITTAEE-FYQSLGIPYHIVNIVS-----GSLNHAASKKLDLEAW 382
1WLE : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	EQSSELLEEFLSLQME-ILTELGLHFRVLDMP-----QELGLPAYRKFDEI.EAW
3QNE : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	EKSWEFDRMIGCSEE-FYQSLGLPYRVVGIVS-----GELNNAAAKKYDLEAW
3LSQ : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	EESWRHLEDMITTSEE-FNKSLGLPYRVVNICS-----GALNNAAAKKYDLEAW
3ERR : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	EASDRAFQELLENAEE-ILRLELLEPYRLVEVAT-----GDMGPGKWRQVDIEVY
1SER : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	EASDRAFQELLENAEE-ILRLELLEPYRLVEVAT-----GDMGPGKWRQVDIEVY
2DQ0 : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	EESWEWHEKIIRNAEE-LFQLELEI.PYRVVNICT-----GDLGYVAAKKYDIEAW
2DQ3 : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	DTSYDELEKLVKDAEE-VLQLLGLPYRVVLELCT-----GDLGFSAAKTYDIEVW
ESC : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	EDSMAALEEMTGHAEK-VLQLLGLPYRKIILCT-----GDMGFGACKTYDLEVW
2CIM : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	EEVLKCAEELHDIRYMHIFNDLIDIEWRKARVTPWFMAQEGLLGLA--EENTVGTDDYEAC
3W3S : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	EEAYRIRRELELEATKR-VAEELELEWVVDPPFYLEGRLLLEDRIEL.PDV.PSYEFVY
:	:	:	:	* : *
3VBB : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	FPGSGAFRELVSCSNCTDYQARRLRIRYQQTKKM---MDKVEFVHMLNATMCATTRTICA 439
1WLE : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	MPGRGRFGEVTSASNCTDFQSRRLHIMFQTE-AG----ELQFAHTVNATGCAVPRLLIA
3QNE : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	FPPQQEYKELVSCSNCTDYQSRNLEIRCGIKQON---QQEKYVHCLNLTLSATERTICC
3LSQ : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	F.PAS.GAFREL.VSCSNCTDY.QSQSVNCR.YGPNL.RGTAAQNVKEYCHMLNGTLCAITRTMCC
3ERR : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LPSEGRYRETHSCSALLDWQARRANLRYRDP-EG----RVRYAYTLNNTALATPRILAM
1SER : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LPSEGRYRETHSCSALLDWQARRANLRYRDP-EG----RVRYAYTLNNTALATPRILAM
2DQ0 : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	MPGQGGKPREVVSASNCTDYQARRLNIRFRDRTDE----KPRYVHTLNSTAIATSRATVA
2DQ3 : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	FPSQNKYREISSCSNCTDYQARRMTRFKDSKTG----KNRFVHTLNGSGLAVGRTLAA
ESC : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	IPAQNTYREISSCSNVWDFQARRMQARCRKSDK----KTRLVHTLNGSGLAVGRTLVA
2CIM : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LPYRGP-----DGEWLEFQNVISINGDKYP--KGFNVKLQSGDELWSGCSGVGLERWAAV
3W3S : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	L.PFK.GERS---SEEAWISV.GSFNVH.GEHPV---DGFNVK.EKSGRT.LFTG.CAGLVTRV.WVV
:	:	:	:	* : *
3VBB : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	I LENYQTEKGI-TVPEKLKEFPPLQELI.PVKPAPIEQEP.SKKQKQHEGS---KKKA 495
1WLE : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LLESYQQKDGSVLPPALQPYLGTD--RITTPTHVPLQYIGPNQPQKPR.LPGQPASS---
3QNE : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	I LENYQKEDGL-VIPEVLRKYIPGE-PEFIPYIKELPKNTTSVKKAKGKNPKNTTSVKKA
3LSQ : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	ICENYQTEEGV-VIPDVLRPYMMGI--EMIRFENNAQAEGTTP-----
3ERR : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LLENHQLQDGRVVRVQALIPYMCKE--VLEPGAHHHHHH-----
1SER : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LLENHQLQDGRVVRVQALIPYMCKE--VLEPCG-----
2DQ0 : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	I LENHQEEDGTVRI.PKVLWKYTGFK--EIVPVEKKERCCAT-----
2DQ3 : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	I LENYQQEDGSVVPEVLRDYVGTD--VIRPE-----
ESC : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	VMENYQQADGRIE.VPEVLR.PYMNGL--EYIG-----
2CIM : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	FLAQKGLDPA--NWPEE.FRNR.VGEMP-KGIRFL-----
3W3S : A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LLAQHGFPY--EWPEPILERIDEKF-GGLPEVP--KTLTWPE-----
:	:	:	:	* : *

3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	AARDVTLLENRLQNMEVTDAL EHHHHHHH	522
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----	
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	KGKNGSRHHHHHH-----	
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----	
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----	
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----	
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----	
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----	
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----	
2CIM:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----	
3W3S:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----	

Fig. S18. The multiple sequence alignment of *Homo sapience*, *Thermus thermophilus*, *Trypanosoma brucei*, *Pyrococcus horikoshi*, *Mus musculus*, *Aquifex aeolicus*, *Bos taurus*, *Candida albicans*, *Escherichia coli*, *Escherichia coli*, *Methanosarcina barkeri*, *Methanopyrus kandleri*.

Fig. 9. (a) Root mean square deviation (RMSD) of Arg349 residue including the side chain of SerRS from *Methanopyrus kandleri* with respect to initial structure (in Å), for open state with tRNA, closed state with tRNA and open state without tRNA. (b) The simulated geometry of the motif 2 and motif 2 loop showing Arg349 in the (1) crystal, 3W3S.pdb, (2) simulated open state and (3) simulated closed state (both states with tRNA).

This indicates that tRNA has long ranged electrostatic interaction with the catalytic domain. (3) Substrate binding organizes the catalytic domain as expected. The effect of substrate is noted in the serine ordering loop (SOL) region. (4) An ordering of the closed state upon substrate binding is noted and is suggestive of an opening-closing

motion. A hinge movement around an axis nearly parallel to H4 is found in the present study. The tRNA influences this hinge type movement as well. It is most important to note that the hinge movements of domains occur in opposite ways in the absence of tRNA in open state and in the absence of tRNA in closed state. Clearly, the hinge motion brings the CCA terminal tRNA closer to the catalytic core which is essential for the reaction and is shown for the first time. The conformation of the connecting loop changes relative to the initial structure upon substrate binding. This indicates a domain organization and is suggestive of a communication between domains upon substrate binding. (5) Finally, the active site residues are more ordered in the closed state compared to the open state and this result corroborates the B-factor results. The paper presents the first study of SerRS dynamics and reveals various conformational changes hitherto unobserved.

Supporting information

Computational methods :

The pdb codes are 3VBB.pdb for *Homo sapience*³⁵, 1SER.pdb for *Thermus thermophilus*³⁰⁻³⁴, 2LSQ for *Trypanosoma brucei*⁴⁴, 2DQ0.pdb for *Pyrococcus horikoshi*²⁹, 3ERR.pdb for *Mus musculus*⁴⁵, 2DQ3.pdb for *Aquifex aeolicus*⁴⁴, 1WLE.pdb for *Bos taurus*²⁶, 3QNE.pdb for *Candida albicans*⁴⁶, 2CIM.pdb for *Methanosarcina barkeri*^{27,28} and 3W3S.pdb for *Methanopyrus kandleri*⁴⁴. The FASTA sequence of *Escherichia coli* is obtained from UniProt database⁴⁷.

The B-factors are computed for C_{α}^N as well as averaged over all heavy atoms (excluding hydrogen atoms). The results are shown in Figs. 2-6 and S1 to S6 in the Supporting information for *Thermus thermophilus*,

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3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----MVLDDLFRVDKGGDPALIRET	22
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	MGHHHHHSSGLVPRGSATERQDRNLLYEHAREGYSALPLLDMESLCAYPE---DAARA	56
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----MLDINAFVLEKGGDPEIIKAS	
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----GPGSMVLDIQFRDETGA--NI TRES	
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----MVDLKLRLQEP---EVFHRA	
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----MVDLKLRLQEP---EVFHRA	
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----MLDIKLIRENP---ELVKND	
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----MIDINLIREKP---DYVKER	
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----MLDPNLLRNEP---DAVAEK	
::* . :					
3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	QE-KR--FKDPGLVDQLVKADSEWRRRCFRADNLNKLNK-----	59
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LDLRKGEELR-SKDLPGIISTWQELRQLREQIRSLEEKEA-----	95
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	QK-KR--GDSVELVDEI TAEYKEWVKLRFDLDEHNKLNLS-----	
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	QR-RR--FADPDIVDAI I EADKKWRRTOFLTEASKLINI-----	
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	IR-EKGV---ALDLEALLAVDEQLHKQEQEVIADKQMSVKEDLDKVEPAVIEAQNVAVKSIIK	
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	IR-EKGV---ALDLEALLAVDEQLHKQEQEVIADKQMSVKEDLDKVEPAVIEAQNVAVKSIIK	
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LI-KRGELEKVKWVDEILKLDTEWRTKLKEINLRLRHERNK-----	
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LA-TRD-KELVSLVDKVLKDRRREI IKRLEALRSERNK-----	
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LA-RRG-FKL--DVDKLGALERRRVLQVKTENLQAERNS-----	
:	:	:	:	:	:
3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----CSKTIG	65
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----VT	97
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----VQKEIG	
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----CSKAVG	
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	KQHLVEVRSMANPPAAVKLALLESIALLLGESTTDWKQIRSIIMRENFIPTIVNFSAEIIS	
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	----VAKRVPKAPPEE-----	
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----IAVEIG	
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----LSKEIG	
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----RSKSIG	
:	:	:	:	:	:
3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	EKMKKKEPVGDESVPENVLSFD---DLTADALANLKVSIKVRLLIDEAILKCAERI	122
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	EAVRALVVNQD-----N-----SQ-VQQDFQYQSLRARGREIRKQLT	144
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	KRFKAKEDAKDLIAEKEKLS-----NEKKEI I	
:	:	:	:	:	:
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	AKKKAKEADGDTSEIPPVQVKEAYENGLTKGEQVEQLCVLQKQSKDLSQVAGLAKEAQ	
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	DAIREMKKNYM-SNPSNYEIVNRSASLAAGPMVKWAIQALNY--ADMLKRVEPLRNLQ	
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----K--EALIARGKALGEEAK	
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	K-----RRKKGEPV--DELLAKSREIVKRIG	
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	K-----LKREGKDT--TEIQNRVKELKEEID	
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	Q-----AKARGEDI--EPLRLEVNKLGEELD	
:	:	:	:	:	:
3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	KLEAER-----FENLREIGNLLHPSVPI SNDEDVDNKVERIWD-----	161
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LLYPKEAQLEEQFYLRALRLPNQTHPDVPGDESQ--ARVLHVVDKPAF-----	
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	EKEAEA---DKNLRSKINQVGNIVHESVDSQDEEN-NELVRTWTPPE-NYKKEP-----	
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	QLEEEER-----DKMLNVGNILHESVPIAQDEETGNTVVRTFGN-----	
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	KLEDDAKDNQQLEALLQVPLPPWPGAPVGGEE-A-NREIKRVGGPPEF-----	
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	RLEEALREKEARLEALLQVPLPPWPGAPVGGEE-A-NREIKRVGGPPEF-----	
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	ELENEVEELKKKIDYLLWRLPNI THPSVPVGDEND-NVPIRFWKGARVWKGHLERFLEQ	
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	RLEEELRKVEEELKNTLLWIPNLPHPSVPVGEDEKD-NVEVRRWGEPRKF-----	
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	AAKAELDALQAEIRDIATIPNLPADEVVPGKDEND-NVEVSRWGTTPREF-----	
:	:	:	:	:	:
3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----CTVRKKYSHVDLVVMVDGFEGEK-GAVVAGSRGYFLKGVLVFLEQALIQYAL	212
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----SFQPRGHLEIAEKLDIIRQKR-LSHVSGHRSYLRGAGALLQHGLVNFLL	
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	---QIAAATGAPAKLSHHEVLLRLDGYDPER-GVRI VGHRYFLRNYGVFLNQALINYGL	
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----TTKRAKLNHVSIMERLGMMDTSAKAVTSMAGGRSYVLKGGVLQVAVLSYSL	
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----SFPPLDHVALMEKNGWWE-PR-ISQVSGRSYALKGDLALYELALLRFAM	
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----SFPPLDHVALMEKNGWWE-PR-ISQVSGRSYALKGDLALYELALLRFAM	
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	SQGMMEYI LEWKPKLHVLDLEILGGADPAR-AAKVSGSRFYLLNEIIVLIDLALIRFAL	
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----DFEKPWHWEIGERLGLDFKR-GAKLSGSRFTVIAGWGARLERALINFML	
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----DFEVRDHVTLGEMHSGLDFAA-AVKLTGSRFVVMKQIARMHRALSQFML	
* :	:	:	:	:	:
3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	RTLGS-RGYIPIYTPFFMRKEVMQEAQLSQFD-EELYKVIKGESEKSDDNSYDEKYLIA	270
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	NKLIH-RGFTPMTVPDLLRGVVFEGCGMTPNAKPSQIYNIDPS-----RFDLNLG	
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	SFLSS-KGYVPLQAPVMMNKEVMAKTAQLSQFD-EELYKVIDGE-----DEKYLIA	
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	DFLVK-RGYTPFYPPFFLNRDMGEVAQLSQFD-EELYQVSGDG-----DKKYLIA	
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	DFMAR-RGFLPMTLPSYAREKAFLGTGHFPAYR-DQVWAI-----A-----ETDLYLTG	
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	DFMAR-RGFLPMTLPSYAREKAFLGTGHFPAYR-DQVWAI-----A-----ETDLYLTG	
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	DRLIE-KGFTPVI PPMYVRRFVEEGSTSFEDFE-DVIYKV-----E---DEDLYLIP	
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	DLHTK-KGYKEICPHLVKPEILIGTGLPKFE-EDLYKC-----E---RDNLYLIP	
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	DLHTEQHGYSSENYVPLVNDTLYGTGLPKFA-GDLFHTRPLEEED---TSNYALIP	
:* :	:	:	:	:	:
3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	TSEQPIAALHRDEWLRP--EDLPIKYAGLSTCFRQEVGSHGRDTRGIFRVHQFEKIEQFV	328
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	TAEVGLAGYFMDHVSFAF--RDLPIRMVCSSTCYRAETD-TGKEPWGLYRVHHFTKVEFMFG	

3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	TSEQPISAYHAGWEFESPAEQLPVRYAGYSSCFRREAGSHGKDAWGI FRVHAFEKIEQFV
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	TSEMPIAAYHRGRWFTE--LKEPLKYAGMSTCFRKEAGAHGRDTLGI FRVHQFDKIEQFV
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	TAEVVLNALHSGEILPY--EALPLRYAGYAPAFRSEAGSFGKDVRGLMRVHQFHKVEQYV
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	TAEVVLNALHSGEILPY--EALPLRYAGYAPAFRSEAGSFGKDVRGLMRVHQFHKVEQYV
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	TAEHPLAGMHANEILDG--KDLPLLYVGVSPCFRKEAGTAGKDTKGI FRVHQFHKVEQFV
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	TAEVPLTNLYREELIKE--ENLPIVLTAYTPCYRREAGAYGKDIRGI IRQHQPDKVELVK
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	TAEVPLTNLVRGEIIDE--DDLPIKMTAHTPCFRSEAGSYGRDTRGLIRMQHFPDKVEMVQ
:	:	:	:	*:* *:* *:* *:* *:* *:*
3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	YSSPHDNKSWEMFEEMITTAEEFYQSLGIPYHIVNIVSGSLNHAASKKLDLEAWFPGSGA 385
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	VTGPGLEQSSLEEFSLQMEILTELGLHFRVLDMPQTQELGLPAYRKFDIEAWMPGRGR
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LTEP--EKSWEFDRMIGCSEEFYQSLGLPYRVVGI VSGELNNAAKKYDLEAWFPQQE
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	VCSPRQESWRHLEDMITTSEEFNKSGLGLPYRVVNICSGALNNAAKKYDLEAWFPASGA
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LTEASLEASDRAFQELLENAEELRLLELPYRLVEVATGDMGPGKWRQVDIEVYLPSEGR
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LTEASLEASDRAFQELLENAEELRLLELPYRLVEVATGDMGPGKWRQVDIEVYLPSEGR
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	YSRP--EESWEWHEKIRNAEELFQELEIPYRVVNICGDLGYVAACKYDIEAWMPGQGK
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	IVHP--DTSYDELEKLVKDAEEVLQLLGLPYRVVLELCTGDLGFSAAKTYDIEVWFPQNK
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	IVRP--EDSMAALEEMTGHAEKVQLLGLPYRKIILCTGDMGFGACKTYDLEVWVIPAQNT
: *	:	:	:	*:* *:* *:* *:* *:* *:*
3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	FRELVSNSCTDYQARRLRIRYQTKM---MDKVEFVHMLNATMCATTRTICAILENYQ 445
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	FGEVTSASNSCTDFQSRRLHIMFQTE-AG----ELQFAHTVNATGCAPVRLLIALLLESYQ
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	YKELVSCNSCTDYQSRNLEIRCGIKQQN---QKEKKYVHCLNSTLSATERTICILENYQ
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	FRELVSNSCTDYQSSVNCRYGPNLRGTAAQNVKEYCHMLNGTLCAITRTMCCICENYQ
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	YRETHSCSALLDQARRANLRYRDP-EG----RVRYAYTLNNTALATPRILAMLENHQ
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	YRETHSCSALLDQARRANLRYRDP-EG----RVRYAYTLNNTALATPRILAMLENHQ
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	FREVVSASNSCTDQARRLNIRFRDRTDE----KPRYVHTLNSTALATSRAIVAILENHQ
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	YREISSCSNCEDFQARRMNTFRKDSKTC----KNRFVHTLNGSGLAVGRTLAAILENYQ
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	YREISSCSNVVDFQARRMQARCRSKSDK----KTRLVHTLNGSGLAVGRTLVAVMENYQ
: *	:	:	:	*:* *:* *:* *:* *:* *:*
3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	TEKGI-TVPEKLFKEMPPGLQELIPFVKPAPIEQEPSKKQKQKQHEGS---KKKAAARDVT 501
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	QKDGSLVPPALQPYLGTD--RITTPHVPVLPQYIGPNQPKPRLPGQPASS-----
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	KEDGL-VIPEVLRKYIPGE-PEFIPIYIKELPKNTTSVKKAKGKNPKNTTSVKKAKGKNGS
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	TEEGV-VIPDVLRYPMGMI--EMIRFENNAQAEGTTP-----
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LQDGRVVRVQALIPYMGKE--VLEPGAHHHHH-----
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LQDGRVVRVQALIPYMGKE--VLEPCG-----
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	EEDGTVRIPKVLWYTGPK--EIVPVEKKERCCAT-----
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	QEDGSVVVPEVLRDYGVTD--VIRPE-----
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	QADGRIEVPEVLRPYMNGL--EYIG-----
. *	:	:	:	*:* *:* *:* *:* *:* *:*
3VBB:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	LENRLQNMEVTDALHHHHHH 522
1WLE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----
3QNE:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	RHHHHHH-----
3LSQ:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----
3ERR:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----
1SER:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----
2DQ0:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----
2DQ3:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----
ESC:A	PDBID	CHAIN	SEQUENCE	-----

Fig. S19. The multiple sequence alignment of *Homo sapience*, *Thermus thermophilus*, *Trypanosoma brucei*, *Pyrococcus horikoshi*, *Mus musculus*, *Aquifex aeolicus*, *Bos taurus*, *Candida albicans*, *Escherichia coli*, *Escherichia coli* and excluding *Methanosarcina barkeri*, *Methanopyrus kandleri*.

Methanosarcina barkeri, *Pyrococcus horikoshi*, *Methanopyrus kandleri* and *Homo sapience*, respectively. Classical MD simulation is performed for SerRS in both open and closed state from *Methanopyrus kandleri* in the bound and unbound states with tRNA. The starting point is the crystal structure 3W3S.pdb. The crystal is engineered where the SerRS belongs to *Methanopyrus kandleri* and tRNA is from *Aquifex aeolicus*. The crystal structure contained few selenomethionine residues and are modified to methaionine for MD simulation. The terminal adenosine base of 3' end of tRNA is absent in the crystal structure. The geometry of the missing adenosine residue

is taken from the CCA terminal of tRNA^{Glu} (2CV1.pdb)⁴⁴. The residue is added at the 3' end of tRNA of tRNA^{Ser}. Substrates (ATP and Ser) and two Mg²⁺ ions are docked at the active site using AutoDock Vina software⁴⁹. The Cartesian coordinates of the substrate ATP is taken from the B chain of crystal structure 2CJA.pdb of organism *Methanosarcina barkeri*. The active site of SerRS is docked with both Ser with -NH₂ group and Ser with -NH₃⁺ (Zwitterionic format). Single water molecule is docked in the tetra coordinated position with Zn²⁺ in the open state.

All simulations are performed using AMBER11 suite of programs⁵⁰. The Ser and ATP parameters are pre-

pared using the antechamber module of AMBER11. The parameters of Zn^{2+} are taken from the standard literature⁵¹. AMBER ff99SB force field⁵²⁻⁵⁴ is used. Total 120 Na^+ ions are added to neutralize the open state bound with tRNA. The system was solvated in an octahedral box of water molecules using TIP3P potential⁵⁵ with 6 Å distance from protein to the edge of the box in each direction. Total 54128 water molecules are added to form a cubic box. Following protocol is used to minimize and equilibrate the system. Only the solvent system is minimized at constant pressure steepest decent method followed by conjugate gradient algorithm. The electrostatic interactions were calculated by using the Particle-mesh Ewald sum^{56,57} with constant pressure periodic boundary condition with the nonbonded cutoff of 10 Å. Isotropic position scaling is used maintain pressure at 1 bar and the pressure relaxation time is 2 ps. Minimization of the whole system at constant pressure with the same condition mentioned above. MD trajectory was generated initially for 50 ps (with 1 fs time step) using Langevine dynamics⁵⁸ and relaxing only solvent molecules at constant pressure and restraining the position of whole protein and whole tRNA restraining the position of whole protein and tRNA with the force constant 500.0 kcal/mol-Å² to equilibrate. The SHAKE algorithm⁵⁹ is used to restrain the bonds linking the heavy atoms and hydrogen atoms. Subsequently, trajectory was generated for 100 ps (with 1 fs time step) relaxing the solvent molecules, substrates (Ser and ATP), side chains of protein and the whole of tRNA keeping restraint only over the backbone of protein at constant pressure. Further 50 ps (with 1 fs time step) trajectory was generated to relax solvent, substrate (Ser and ATP), whole of protein and whole of tRNA (complete system) at constant pressure (NPT). The potential, kinetic energies as well as other parameters were checked to confirm that the system is equilibrated. The potential energy and kinetic energy of the system are stable during the production run. Subsequently, 500 ps trajectory was generated relaxing whole system and used for analysis. Summarizing, 700 ps molecular dynamics simulation is carried out including 200 ps equilibration and 500 ps production run (used for analysis). The multiple sequence alignments are performed using Clustal Omega^{47,48}.

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